

RTBV. Those that gave negative transmission were identified as plants infected with RTBV alone.

Plants infected with RTSV alone were identified next. Virus-free leafhoppers were given 24 h access to each healthy-looking plant inoculated with RTSV alone, followed by an 8 h or overnight acquisition access to previously identified RTBV-infected plants. The insects were then used to inoculate 7-d-old TN1 seedlings as above. Plants that gave posi-

tive transmission were identified as RTSV-infected while those that gave negative transmission were identified as healthy plants.

In this experiment, TN1 seedlings were inoculated with tungro using plants infected with both virus particles. Sixteen inoculated plants with moderate stunting and discoloration were tested: 2 plants had both RTBV and RTSV and 14 had RTBV alone. Fourteen symptomless plants inoculated with RTSV done were

used for RTSV detection: 12 plants had RTSV and 2 were healthy.

To test the accuracy of this method, the virus particles present in each plant were counterchecked serologically with a latex test. Results of the serological test showed that the method was accurate.

This method takes about 10 d to detect RTBV-infected plants and another 10 d to detect RTSV. In contrast, results by serology and electron microscopy are obtained in only a few hours. □

Quality of rice grains from sheath rot-affected plants

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Sheath rot caused by *Acrocyndrium* (= *Sarocladium*) *oryzae* Sawada is a major rice disease in India. We recorded changes in grain quality caused by the disease.

Trials with ADT31 and ADT36, both popular varieties in Tamil Nadu, were conducted during 1982 kuruvai. The disease intensity was arbitrarily classified into 5 grades (0, 3, 5, 7, 9) based upon the lesions on the leaf sheath near the panicle. 0 indicated no infection; 9 indicated the boot leaf sheath was completely infected and the panicle could not emerge. No grains formed in plants scoring 9.

Rice grains were harvested from individual plants with various disease intensity levels. Grains also were collected from

Changes in rice grain quality due to sheath rot incidence in 2 rice cultivars.

Disease intensity grade	Discolored grains				1000-grain wt (g)		Seed germination (%)		Protein content (%) of ADT36
	no./panicle		%panicle						
	ADT31	ADT36	ADT31	ADT36	ADT31	ADT36	ADT31	ADT36	
0	1	2	0.9	1.4	15.7	15.7	94	97	8.0
3	19	54	18.1	38.3	12.3	15.3	89	92	7.5
5	60	78	66.7	67.8	6.3	11.5	76	81	4.4
7	85	94	97.7	93.1	4.9	8.7	58	63	2.2
9	^a								

^aNo grains were formed.

healthy plants. One hundred panicles were collected for each disease intensity category.

Discolored and healthy grains from each panicle were counted. The 1,000-grain weight was measured by taking 4 samples in each category. Germination of seeds from each category was assessed by using the roll towel method and 400 seeds for each infection level. Protein content of ADT36 grains was assessed by estimating total nitrogen content by the micro-Kjeldahl method and multiplying it by 6.25. Two independent experiments, each with four replications, were conducted.

Disease of the boot leaf sheath caused discolored grains (see table). Although many different causes of grain discoloration have been reported, this is the first time that *Acrocyndrium oryzae* has been reported as a cause. Attempts to isolate the fungus from the discolored grains failed, which suggests that the fungus causes grain discoloration by inducing a physiological change.

The disease reduced the 1,000-grain weight and caused poor grain filling, which reduced seed germination (see table). Protein content of the grains was also affected. □

Leaf scald disease of rice in Karnataka, India

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Leaf scald disease of rice caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae* was observed for the first time in Karnataka in Oct 1982 on Intan rice. Intan was very susceptible to the disease and had lesions covering more than 50% of the leaf area. Seed

Table 1. Incidence of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* on seeds from Karnataka State districts, India (400 seeds tested per sample following blotter method).

District	Samples tested (no.)	Infected samples (no.)	Samples (no.) at given range (%) of infection						
			0.5-5	6-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-64
Belgaum	2	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—
Bellari	1	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Chikmagalur	3	1	—	—	—	—	1	—	—
Chitradurga	4	3	2	—	1	—	—	—	—
Dharwar	5	1	—	—	1	—	—	—	—
Hassan	7	4	3	1	—	—	—	—	—
Kodagu	5	5	—	—	2	—	1	1	1
Mandya	3	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mysore	20	19	9	7	1	2	—	—	—
Total	50	31	18	8	5	2	2	1	1

Table 2. Incidence of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* in parts of rice seed.

Variety	Infection (%) in			
	Husk	Endo-sperm	Embryo	Whole seed
IR8	12	14	12	13
Intan	30	17	10	64
Palguna	13	17	14	22
Average	18	16	12	33

Effect of organic and inorganic chemicals on in vitro growth of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*

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The in vitro effect of 235 chemical compounds on the growth of 34 *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* strains was tested in agar media. The chemicals tested were al-

cohols, aldehydes, organic and inorganic salts and acids, oximes, quaternary ammonium compounds, amines, glycosides, ketones, oxides, phenolic compounds, and sulfoxides. The chemicals were tested at a concentration of 0.005% (wt/vol), and those that prevented development of all 34 strains at 0.005% were tested at lower concentrations. A multipoint inoculator was used to inoculate the media.

The most active products against *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* in vitro were ZnO,

8-hydroxyquinoline, and methylglyoxal (all inhibitory between 0.0005% and 0.001%); Cd (NO₃)₂ Cd (OOC.CH₃)₂, o-phenanthroline, 7-chloro-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-1-ethyl-3-quinoline carboxylic acid (CGA 78039), and formaldehyde (inhibitory between 0.0001% and 0.0005%). Salts of copper, nickel, and cobalt were inhibitory for all strains at concentrations between 0.001% and 0.005%. Promising compounds will be tested further in field trials at IRRI. □

embryo were separated after seeds were soaked in sterile water for 4 h and surface sterilized with 0.5% NaOCl for 10 min. *R. oryzae* was counted using the standard blotter method.

Production of inocula of *Rhizoctonia solani* on different media and media effect on disease development

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Since its inception, BRRI has screened rice varieties for resistance to sheath blight (ShB) caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*. We first used inocula prepared in potato dextrose agar (PDA) and later used inocula grown in rice:rice hull (R:RH). R: RH medium, although inexpensive and easy to prepare, often was contaminated by fungi or bacteria (probably spore forming), even after double sterilization. We tested a new media for large-scale production of *R. solani* inocula.

The media and varieties used are in Tables 1 and 2. Equal amounts of inocula were raised for inoculum production and for inoculating the rice plants. Growth characters of the fungus on different media, lesion length development/d (growth rate), and disease index (DI) at maturity were recorded for all varieties and media used.

R: RH and rice straw (RS) media gave

cohols, aldehydes, organic and inorganic salts and acids, oximes, quaternary ammonium compounds, amines, glycosides, ketones, oxides, phenolic compounds, and sulfoxides. The chemicals were tested at a concentration of 0.005% (wt/vol), and those that prevented development of all 34 strains at 0.005% were tested at lower concentrations. A multipoint inoculator was used to inoculate the media.

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Table 1. Effect of inocula prepared in different media on *Rhizoctonia solani* growth and sheath blight development.

Media	Growth character				Sheath blight development	
	Mycelial	Sclerotial initiation ^a	Sclerotia production	Contamination %	Rate (mm/d) ^b	DI ^c
R:RH (1:2)	Slow	11	Low	Moderate	13.7 a	5.1 a
RS	Slow	11	Low	Low	12.3 a	4.8 a
RC (green)	Medium	6	High	Nil	14.1 a	4.6 ab
WH	Fast	5	Moderate	Nil	13.8 a	5.0 a
RC:WH (1:1)	Fast	5	High	Nil	12.1 a	4.7 ab
RC:WH (2:1)	Fast	5	High	Nil	14.9 a	5.0 a
RC:WH (1:2)	Fast	5	Moderate	Nil	13.0 a	4.8 a
PDA	Very fast	2	High	Low	13.4 a	4.4 b

^a Indicates days after inoculation. ^b Measured as mean lesion length development in mm/day. ^c DI = disease index (severity), measured on a scale of 0-9.

Table 2. Effect of inocula of *Rhizoctonia solani* prepared in three media on sheath blight development on 8 rice varieties.

Variety inoculated	Disease development as lesion length in mm/day ^a				Disease ^b reaction
	PDA	WH	RC	Mean	
BR1	16.0	21.7	25.5	21.1 a	S
IR8	20.4	18.7	18.6	19.2 ab	MS
Chianung Sen Yu-6	19.2	19.1	19.2	19.2 ab	MS
BR3	19.6	17.0	20.1	18.9 ab	MS
Dular	18.5	17.6	17.7	17.9 b	MR
Dharial	19.0	18.7	16.1	17.9 b	MR
BR8	13.8	12.6	13.4	13.3 b	MR
BR9	11.6	12.0	12.6	12.1 b	MR

^a Mean of 32 isolates. ^b S = susceptible, MS = moderately susceptible, MR = moderately resistant.